

A spotlight on the vibrant north west chemicals sector

Elements

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A Northwest entrepreneur with a quest to assist in reducing petrochemical reliance attracts some Royal attention

Paul H. Jones, Managing Director of Anacarda Ltd and Bitrez Ltd, both current Queens award for Enterprise winners in the innovation category for specialty polymer manufacturing, completed a clean sweep with his third business. Chemical Processing Services Ltd (CPS) was awarded an inaugural Kings Award for Enterprise 2023, again in the innovation category.

The King welcomed recipients of The King's Award for Enterprise to Buckingham Palace, joined by The Duke and Duchess of Edinburgh and The Duke and Duchess of Gloucester. Paul attended the function for which the Lancashire-based company had secured the award for its recently Patented technology. Paul coined the term Furalkamine for the bio-based technology he developed which is being used to extend the lifespan of products, as part of his holistic view to environmental improvement.

The awards citation says "The unique chemical structure imparts exceptionally high chemical and acid resistance. This allows the formulation of systems that can operate in the most hostile environments, withstand the most arduous conditions, and provide resilient bond lines and protective coatings."

Paul said: "I'm delighted that CPS has won the Inaugural King's Award for Enterprise especially in the innovation category. This specialist business was set up to develop new disruptive technology and it is an honour and a privilege to be recognised with this award".

With little time to rest, Paul had to switch hats back to his Bitrez demands with the second FOREST (Advanced lightweight materials FOR Energy-efficient STructures) EU Horizon funded consortium meeting, being hosted at the Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials in Bremen, Germany. This meeting brought together consortium members for an opportunity to meet, present, and discuss project progression.

The Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials IFAM has its main location in the Technology Park Bremen. With approximately 400 employees working on sustainable innovations for industry and society, the IFAM scientists carry out research and development work in interdisciplinary teams for various industrial sectors and application areas.

Consortium members pictured outside the meeting venue.

Key personnel from IFAM are working with Paul on the development and enhancement of biobased Benzoxazines with an aim to increase the biogenic Carbon content, enhance the fire resistance, and generate matrix systems that will aid lightweighting in the electrification of vehicles whilst satisfying the arduous specification requirements.

With the support, guidance, and assistance of his preferred European Patent Attorneys Mathys & Squire who have aided the accelerated Grant of several of the CPS patents through the UK Green Channel, Pauls' latest Patent to Grant is the Bio-Benzoxazines that are forming part of the FOREST project and included within the schedule of works. Paul is also looking at opportunities to work with other organisations seeking similar goals and objectives in the hope of forming clusters, enabling further technical sharing and dissemination of information that may support industry progress in the route to decarbonisation. The aim of this project is fully aligned with EU 2030 Climate and Energy challenges.

Paul commented, "We are always looking for opportunities to contribute and support the scientific community in turn changing the face of industrial practice and rectifying anthropogenic damage. I have said it before, but I feel honoured to be part of the FOREST project and able to work alongside the creative partners that form the consortia. We are pushing boundaries with disruptive bio-based polymers, I believe that collectively we will accomplish our target requirements and we will succeed in bringing sustainable and recycled materials to the transport sector to aid their quest to reduce fossil fuel dependency, electrify, and further lightweight for efficiency.

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For further details visit <https://www.cps-consultancy.com/> or <https://www.bitrez.com/> To read more about the FOREST project visit - <https://www.forest-project.eu/>

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